

APPLICATION OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION - STANDARDS

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Abstract. *The article describes the use of pedagogical and innovative technology in education. An attempt has been made to demonstrate its goals, objectives and achievement in education, with its effectiveness analyzed and results and other differences.*

Keywords: *pedagogical technology, innovation, educational reform, learning process, student and teacher activity, continuous learning, motivation, innovation management, control, change mechanism.*

INTRODUCTION. In the course of the deep reform in the Republic by strengthening its independence, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan " State Youth Policy" fully developed, initiative, modern technology, independently thinking, responsible for the future of the country in accordance with the requirements of the present time. to educate young talented professionals who mobilize all their might and potential for the benefit of the people, realize their intellectual and creative potential One of the most pressing problems is the creation of a sound legal framework for issuing. It should be noted that the "Strategy of Action for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021" defines a number of new and important tasks related to increasing the activity of young people in the reforms aimed at building a democratic state and civil society. At the beginning of the article, great work is being done to ensure consistent and effective implementation of the state youth policy, especially the radical reform of the education system. In this regard, one of the urgent tasks of the changes under the Education Act, the National Program for Personnel Training and the ongoing education reforms is to create a freely and independent thinker, a conscious and active participant in the social and political life. The main purpose of this article is to present a young professional entering society, to meet his own requirements, to prepare himself for life as a master, and to have the opportunity to become a mature and perfect person with his scientific potential. The growth of such individuals will allow the introduction of democracy in the socio-political life of the country, and the full understanding of the duties and responsibilities of civil society and the accelerated construction of a law-governed state. Today, 30 percent of the country's population are young people between the ages of 14 and 30. Wide conditions are created for their education and training. At the same time, the organization of meaningful leisure for young people is a pressing issue. The more young people are spiritually mature, the stronger their immunity to foreigners. As it is known, the head of our state put forward five important initiatives on the creation of new systems in social, spiritual and educational spheres. Upbringing of young people is of great importance in the policy of our country where the primary tasks were defined. Based on these programs, projects in each area were developed. At the meeting, suggestions for these programs and mechanisms for their implementation were

discussed. “The first initiative has prepared a draft program to involve young people in cultural and art institutions. It is expected to approve regional roadmaps to attract 2 million young people between 14 and 30 years of age and culture in 2019-2020, as well as additional classes in children's music and art schools, musical centers, art centers and fine arts. Establishment of clubs, amateur theater groups and children's ensembles. Shavkat Mirziyoev said that the draft program lacks mechanisms for implementation of activities and the practical functions of industry professionals assigned to each city and district as creative consultants are not clearly defined. He stressed the need for a systematic organization of regional road maps, encouraging children from all walks of life, and organizing various competitions, including the construction, reconstruction and overhaul, as well as providing musical centers for cultural centers, schools of music and art. to allocate appropriate funds. The program, designed to attract young people to physical culture and sports, to increase the capacity of sports facilities, is set to build small gyms with sandwich panels in each district within the next two years. The President noted the need for greater involvement of the population and youth in the existing and newly built sports facilities, and the need to increase the number of mass sporting events. The third initiative is the establishment of digital training centers and training centers in districts and cities in 2019-2020 as part of a program to improve the efficiency of computer and Internet use among the population and youth, connecting about 19,000 social network facilities to high-speed Internet access. is being delayed. The participants of the meeting were given instructions on improving computer literacy of the population, directing children interested in information technologies and bringing them to the level of qualified specialists, creation of software products. The Fourth Initiative is aimed at the implementation of the draft program of measures to increase the spirituality of the youth, to popularize reading among them. It is planned to deliver 1 million books to each region on fiction, historical, scientific and popular topics. It is planned to create conditions for the formation of artistic perceptions of future teachers, as well as reconstruction and overhaul of information and library centers, opening of public libraries by entrepreneurs. On the fifth initiative, a draft program of measures to organize sewing and knitwear production and employment of women in the regions was prepared. In 2019-2020, it is planned to build lightweight sewing and knitting factories in each district and employ women. At the meeting, suggestions were made on the establishment of a thorough accounting of these enterprises, finding the market for their goods, that is, the actual buyer”. In every area, education, training, education and training need to be established and reformed. For this purpose, there is a need to use and apply new pedagogical and innovative technologies in education. Many scientists and leading educators do a great job in this regard. Outstanding scientists of the Republic of Uzbekistan N.Saidakhmedov, KO Tolipov, NN Azizkhodjaeva, UN Nishonaliev, B. Farberman, M. Kamoliddinov, B. Ziyomammedov, M. Tadzhiyev, A. Abdurkarimov, A. Paradaev , JG Yuldashev and R.Ishmuhamedov have done a great job in this area with their scientific potential. Today, it is impossible to imagine the educational process without new modern technologies, so every educational process must be implemented through new pedagogical and innovative technologies. The scientific novelty of the article is that not every creative teacher should be able to organize his or her profession today without pedagogical and innovative technology. In this regard, the teacher creates and improves the most relevant, necessary and most effective ways, methods and forms of teaching that will enable the teacher to engage the student in the learning process and for him or her. After all, the main source of strength for a teacher is the student. Their interests and aspirations inspire the teacher. As a result, the terms “pedagogical technology” and

“pedagogical innovation” are formed. Undoubtedly, the main content in this process is education. It requires extensive use of the possibilities of pedagogical technology in research aimed at identifying the place and level of education currently being carried out in various educational institutions. Only then can the results of the educational process contribute to the development of science, industry, culture, economy and all spheres of public life. Only theories based on pedagogical technology can provide a basis for pre-designing the content, forms and means of continuous education, its stages and components, and the impact of educational outcomes on society. Consequently, the transformation of the educational process into new principles and new ideologies, new teaching methods, and reforms in the field of education are possible and necessary. Pedagogical technology is the process by which a teacher influences his students in certain conditions through the use of learning tools, and the intensive formulation of the personality traits predetermined by them. Pedagogical technology is a systematic category that determines the technological process of the educational process. Pedagogical publications also use the terms "technology of instruction" and "technology of education." The implementation of the National Program for Personnel Training entails the introduction of new pedagogical technologies into the content of the second level of education. This imposes responsibility on all teachers. Scientists of the Republic strive to create scientifically grounded educational technologies and adapt them to the socio-pedagogical conditions of Uzbekistan and apply them in educational practice. In pedagogical literature such concepts as "Pedagogical technology", "New pedagogical technology", "Advanced pedagogical technology" are widely used and interpreted differently. The following is the definition given by UNESCO: "Pedagogical technology is a systematic way of creating, using and defining technical and human resources and their interrelationship, which is the task of all learning and knowledge efficiency".

The word technology is Greek, and "techne" is skill, art; "Logos" means education. It refers to the set of methods and techniques used in the manufacturing process to obtain finished products in industry or agriculture. With regard to the learning process, this understanding means the interdependence of reading and learning, the separation of the stages of communication, the coordination of work to achieve the stated objectives of the educational process, their sequential and gradual implementation, and the proper execution of all planned activities and activities. In other words, the concept of educational technology means the art of teaching and the art of teaching. New pedagogical technology refers to the use of the art of teaching, its effective organization, and its enhancement to international standards. The term pedagogical technology is based on a systematic approach to the educational process that has unique characteristics and characteristics, which is an innovative approach to the educational process. Advanced methods and techniques used in the world practice of pedagogy in the creation of new education means the introduction of technical forms of teaching into the learning process, taking into account the individual, mental, intellectual, national and social features of each student. The new pedagogical technology requires that the learner be treated as the subject, ie the active participant of the learning process, and the learner as the organizer and leader of the process. The student is an active person who regains the knowledge he has acquired throughout the course of training, partly applies it to new conditions, implements his mental activities and moves from unknown to known: The essence of the new pedagogical technology is to teach the student to think independently, to stimulate the interest and need for knowledge, to feel the pleasure of discovering it; The aim is to provide students with the opportunity to express themselves in the teaching and learning technologies; The

most important requirement for teaching technology in the course of pedagogical technology is learning based on the student's life experience, previously acquired knowledge and interests. In the process of practical training on new pedagogical technologies the following are the main parameters of education:

1. The whole learning situation is the object of control;
2. Educational management is purposeful and involves the development of meaningful, spiritual and psychological strength of the learner;
3. The educational process is carried out in a democratic, encouraging manner;
4. The essential prerequisite for the educational process is to encourage the student's own initiative, the openness of the teacher, their cooperation, and the building of trust. Pedagogical technology has its own principles:

1. Formulate the main goal of a particular lesson, topic, section, or subject;
2. Divide the lesson or subject matter into the modules, using a common purpose, to define the purpose of each module and the system of issues to be addressed within the modules;
3. Develop test questions for each of the issues to be solved in the module;
4. Select methods of achieving the goals and identify the specific areas where they will be used;
5. Pay particular attention to the necessary connections and interdisciplinary links between the parts of the lesson. The literature and articles on new pedagogical technologies speak about a number of teaching methods.

These methods are presented as innovative methods. Here are some of the methods you can use in Uzbek language classes:

1. Modular learning technology It is aimed at developing students' ability to work independently with textbooks, scholarly and additional literature, and to develop creative and independent thinking. A distinctive feature of modular learning technology is the creation of a modular program that allows students to work independently and creatively on the subject matter.

2. Collaborative Learning Technology. Its main idea is not only to complete the learning tasks, but also to teach the students to collaborate, to create mutual support and exchange of ideas.

3. Technology of problem education. The challenge is to create a situation, ask questions, propose issues and assignments, organize discussions to resolve the problem and validate the conclusions.

4. Technology of interactive methods. Relying on students' creativity, creating an atmosphere of free discussion in the classroom. For this purpose, the class is divided into subgroups, and the class is dealt with during these sessions.

5. Technology of didactic games. The use of different didactic games during the lessons and using them to revitalize the classroom, to stimulate activity and interest.

6. Test lessons. There are lessons to test students' specific knowledge and skills, either through tests or checklists.

With the introduction of the term "technology" in pedagogical activity, the pedagogical practice, its theoretical aspects and the assumptions about them are becoming more scientific. Pedagogical technology is the product of the development of modern didactics and pedagogy. It can be considered as a new step towards a higher level of accomplishment of tasks in all existing and improving main directions of pedagogy. From this point of view, it is necessary to study the pedagogical technology, first and foremost, as a result of the development of modern pedagogical

science, to study its principles and rules, and eventually to identify its laws. Pedagogical technology should, first of all, be considered a social phenomenon that consists of the activities of people (teachers, parents, the public) to meet the needs of further development of education. Like any social phenomenon, there is a field of science that explores pedagogical technology as a science of pedagogical technology. This discipline, in turn, is divided into theoretical and academic disciplines that explore the most feasible ways and methods of modern education. At the same time, pedagogical technology as a direction of practical activity includes principles, algorithms and control systems used in the educational process, as well as the educational process. Pedagogical technology is manifested in different ways as a result of the interconnectedness and development of various spheres of social life. These are the following types of pedagogical technologies: social phenomena, theoretical science, science, teaching, educational system, process, pedagogical activity and its methodology, and related research areas. Pedagogical technology as a social phenomenon arises from the motives associated with the issues of education: need, demand, interest, interest, goals, and serves to achieve them. At the same time, the same motivations exist in every person and family. Increasing the level of knowledge of each member of society is one of the main conditions for the development of this society and the state. The fulfillment of this condition, in turn, depends on the high level of pedagogy and technology. From this, it is evident that pedagogical technology is a social phenomenon that is important in the life of a person, family, society, and state. Pedagogical technology is a complex and inexplicable pedagogical process as an area of knowledge related to human consciousness and thinking. Its peculiarity is that it also covers the problem of upbringing. Thus, the effectiveness of technology depends on how many aspects of a human being are fully represented in it, and how its psychological and professional aspects are taken into account, and their future development (or decline). In this respect, technology also has the capability to design, diagnose, and develop stages of an individual's development. It depends on the teacher's ability to work with the technological process. Introduction of innovations in the education system, effective use of modern pedagogical technologies is one of the main tasks of today's education. Indeed, modern pedagogical technologies have enhanced the effectiveness of the educational process, promotes students' independent thinking, enhances their enthusiasm and interest in knowledge, and enhances their ability to apply knowledge in practice. "Pedagogical Technology" and Innovation mean innovation. Therefore, the innovations should be aimed at improving the quality of the system's goals. In the "National Program for Personnel Training", training, retraining and advanced training of specialists who meet the requirements of modern science, technology and production technologies are assigned to secondary special and educational institutions, which are responsible for the organization, organization of work and training of teaching staff. and the training and retraining of existing staff. Pedagogical technology is essentially the same as other technologies, as others have their own domain, methods and tools, but work with a specific material. production is different from biological and even information technology. Its peculiarity is that it combines educational components. Pedagogical technology with new technological processes in other fields will have new opportunities to influence the process of continuous and traditional learning. Students will be able to organize and manage cognitive activity based on pedagogical technology, which will become a close support for the teacher or complete his or her functions. As a result, logically linked short-cuts are followed so that learners make almost no mistakes and enable the learner to report their results and take new steps towards the full realization of the learning

objective. Innovative activity is the creative approach of the teacher to master the existing forms and tools for self-improvement. It is also worth noting that stable and widely accepted scientific notions and classifications about educational innovations and innovative pedagogical activities have not yet been fully compiled. One of the main reasons for this is the hardships and difficulties that can be overcome between the educational systems of education. The bigger reason is the disconnect between educational knowledge and practical pedagogical activities. The teacher participates in the creation, implementation and promotion of innovation as a subject and organizer of innovative activities.

The goal of innovation is to get the best results from the investment or effort. Unlike other spontaneous innovations, innovation is a mechanism for controlled and controlled change. An innovative process is the process of preparing for and implementing innovative changes. I.P. Based on the study of trends in innovation in the podcast pedagogical system, it establishes: - A complete change of the pedagogical system. - Changes in the learning process. - Changes in pedagogical theory. - Changes in teacher activity. - Updating student activities. - Changes in pedagogical technology. - Content Update. - Changes in forms, methods and means of education. - Change in management. - Change of purpose and result Innovative changes in the learning process, and any updates to the education system are made directly by updating and modifying teacher activities. There is an opportunity to describe the concept of innovation activity through the analysis of innovation in the education system, their implementation and management of innovation processes. Innovative activities are the driving force behind the pedagogical team. Innovation activity is a continuous innovation based on a long-term development and improvement. Based on the foregoing, we created a questionnaire with students from a number of institutions, including higher education institutions, and share some of their findings: In the questionnaire, the higher educational institutions that use the most pedagogical technologies were quoted: 15.5% in Urgench State University, 10.2% in Nukus DPI, 10.2% in TTF Fergana branch. used in the construction institute.5%, in Chirchik SPI 5.2%. In terms of science, the most commonly used subjects in teaching technology are 33.2% in Engineering and Engineering, 27.2% in Social Sciences and Pedagogy. Up to 13.9% in information technology and informatics. The least used pedagogical technologies are Philology and Foreign Language - 2.8%, Medical Science - 5.2%, and Science - 7.4%. The university, which uses the most pedagogical technologies in the educational process, is used in Andijan State University - 86.7%, Nukus DPI - 76.3%, UrgechSU and Karshi State University - 71.9%, Samarkand DSU - 45.0%, Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute using the least pedagogical technologies - 22.5. % Used in Bukhara State University and up to 26.7%. Teachers are most active in teaching methods, seminars, discussions, student reports and interactive methods (brainstorming, small group work, project methodology). 72.2% of students believe that the use of interactive methods and technologies in the learning process can improve the quality of education, and that the ability to use them depends on the teacher at 19.8%. 75.4% of students are evaluated as having a positive impact. GulistanDU has the highest rates of Internet use - 48.2%, Andijan University - 49.2% and Karshi State University 56.4%. As you can see, not all regions have the same information technology. There are universities that use pedagogical technologies, but there are also universities where pedagogical technologies are not used. Therefore, the mission and goal of every educator is to imitate the world educational standards in the clearest context of our state policy and to bring the quality of education to the highest level. Unless every individual

in the community does his or her job in accordance with the requirements of the time, it is already technologically inefficient, and no one needs such a specialist.

It is well-known that the qualities and qualities of a person are formed in the course of their functioning and are the result of their activities. Therefore, teachers need to instill in their psychology the need for novelty and the need for independent reading. For it is more pleasant to man than to glory. If the task of preparing teachers for innovation is in the process of professional development, the implementation of advanced pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process will be more effective and will achieve the expected results from the system of distance learning. In a nutshell. Introduction of new pedagogical technologies into the educational process is a requirement of the time. It depends on the teacher. The teacher must be creative, create new forms and methods of new pedagogical technologies, and skillfully support them in the educational process. Which one of them is the most effective and appropriate for the teacher, and it is advisable to use these technologies.

1. Any innovation or pedagogical technology used must be relevant to the content of education and have the potential to contribute to:

2. Every technology used is age-appropriate and can be of interest and interest:

3. All pedagogical technologies have the potential to promote learning content and make a good impression on the student:

4. All pedagogical and innovative technologies used in education must adhere to the standards of education or do not have excessive noise and freedom in the classrooms and the auditoriums:

5. When using any educational technology, it is necessary to follow the rules of life safety. In conclusion, if every educator aligns with his or her duties to achieve high effectiveness of educational reforms,

I believe that our country will soon be among the world's best-educated countries and justify the President's trust in our teachers.

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